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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation Anal Inflammation (Hemorrhoids) Herbal Cream of *Euphorbia Millii* Leaves

Sujata Samant*, Jija Lode, Priyanka Boratwar, Aishwary Kalbhut, Samir Pandhare

Abhinav Bahu-Uddeshiya Shikshan Sanstha's Siddhivinayak College of Pharmacy, Warora, Chandrapur, Maharashtra, India 442914

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ABSTRACT

Hemorrhoids, also known as piles, are a prevalent anorectal condition characterized by inflammation, pain, bleeding, and swelling of the anal and rectal veins. Conventional treatment options, although effective, often pose risks of side effects and recurrence. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a topical herbal hemorrhoid cream aimed at reducing anal inflammation with minimal side effects. The cream was developed using natural plant-based ingredients with known anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and wound-healing properties. *Euphorbia milii* leaf extract was selected as the primary active ingredient due to its traditional usage and documented pharmacological benefits. The formulation was prepared using an oil in-water (O/W) emulsion base and evaluated for its physical characteristics (appearance, pH, viscosity, spreadability), microbial load, and in vitro antimicrobial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using Amoxycylav 625 as a standard. The results demonstrated that the formulated cream had favorable physicochemical properties and exhibited significant antimicrobial activity, suggesting its potential as an alternative treatment for hemorrhoidal inflammation. Further clinical studies are warranted to confirm its efficacy and safety in human subjects.

INTRODUCTION

HAEMORRHOIDS

Haemorrhoids is a common perianal disease, which often causes haematochezia. Besides a

surgical operation or minimally invasive treatment. Haemorrhoids are swelling and inflammation of veins in the rectum and anus. The anatomical term "haemorrhoids" technically refers to "cushions of tissue filled with blood vessels at the junction of the rectum and the anus". However,

*Corresponding Author: Sujata Samant

Address: Abhinav Bahu-Uddeshiya Shikshan Sanstha's Siddhivinayak College of Pharmacy, Warora, Chandrapur, Maharashtra, India 442914

Email ✉: sujatasamant1357@gmail.com

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the term is popularly used to refer to varicosity of the haemorrhoid tissue. Perianal hematoma are sometimes mis diagnose and mis labelled as haemorrhoids, when in fact they have different causes and treatments. Haemorrhoids may result from straining to move stool. Other contributing factors include pregnancy, aging, chronic constipation or diarrhoea, and anal intercourse[3]. Haemorrhoids are either inside the anus internal or under the skin around the anus external. Haemorrhoids develop from 2 different places.

Haemorrhoids also called piles, are swollen veins in your anus and lower rectum, similar to Herbal medicines are one type of dietary Supplement. They are sold as tablets, capsules, varicose veins. Haemorrhoids can develop inside the rectum (internal Haemorrhoids) or under the skin around the anus (external Haemorrhoids) Depending on anal origin within anal canal and relation to dentate line Haemorrhoids divided in to internal haemorrhoids, external haemorrhoids, mixed haemorrhoid^[1,2].

Fig.no.1: Haemorrhoids

Haemorrhoids are swollen and inflamed veins located in the rectal and anal regions, often leading to discomfort and bleeding. They typically develop due to increased pressure in these veins, which can result from straining during bowel movements, obesity, or pregnancy. External haemorrhoids appear as painful or tender lumps beneath the skin around the anus. These are essentially enlarged blood vessels that become irritated, especially during difficult or strained bowel movements. Common factors contributing to haemorrhoids include: Straining during bowel movements, often due to chronic constipation or diarrhoea. Weakening of supportive tissues with age, which reduces the structural integrity of the anal and rectal veins. Pregnancy, as the growing uterus increases pressure on the pelvic veins. Obesity, which adds extra pressure to the lower

body and veins. Frequent heavy lifting, which can increase abdominal pressure. Low-fiber diets, which contribute to constipation, increasing the risk of haemorrhoids^[4].

CLASSIFICATION

Depending on anal origin within anal canal and relation to dentate line haemorrhoids divided in to

- I. Internal haemorrhoids.
- II. External haemorrhoids.
- III. Mixed haemorrhoids.

TYPES OF HEMORRHOIDS

1. External Haemorrhoids- These are under the skin around your anus. Sign & symptoms might include. Itching or irritation in your anal region.

Pain or discomfort Swelling around your anus
Bleeding

2. Internal Haemorrhoids- Internal haemorrhoids lie inside the rectum. You usually Can't see or feel them, they rarely cause discomfort. Painless bleeding during bowel movements A haemorrhoid to push through the anal opening resulting in pain & irritation. If blood pools in an external haemorrhoids & forms a clot (thrombus) it can result in –

- Severe pain
- Swelling
- Inflammation

- A hard lump near your anus

CAUSES- • The vein around your anus tend to stretch under pressure of may bulge or swell. Haemorrhoids can develop from increased pressure in the lower rectum due to Straining during bowel movement • Sitting for long periods of time on the toilet. For Internal haemorrhoids

- Grade I - bleeding without prolapse
- Grade II - prolapse with spontaneous reduction
- Grade III - prolapse with manual reduction.
- Grade IV-incarcerated, irreducible prolapse^[1]

Fig.no 2: Internal Haemorrhoids grading system

CREAM:

The creams are considered an important part of the cosmetic product as a topical preparation since ancient times due to their relief on the skin and its removal. From cosmetic purposes, Medicinal creams have a variety of applications such as cleansing, beautifying, changing appearance, moisturizing etc. It also plays a vital role in treating skin conditions. These include protecting the skin from bacterial and fungal infections, and promoting the healing of minor cuts, burns, and sores. These fragile arrangements are safe for public and private use. Human skin is vulnerable to damage but has the potential to heal itself. However, a natural healing process can take time and there is also a risk of infection especially in the

early stages of injury. In such cases, medicinal creams can be applied to the injured area to speed up the healing process and prevent the wound from becoming infected. This review emphasizes the use of drug delivery systems in topical formulations, specifically focusing on wound healing creams. It includes an overview of the wound healing process, formulation techniques for creams, their classification according to therapeutic action, benefits and limitations, key features, types of creams, and the various parameters used to evaluate their effectiveness^[5,6].

TYPES OF CREAM

They are divided into two types:

Oil-in-Water (O/W) creams are emulsions where small oil droplets are evenly distributed within a continuous water phase. In this type of formulation, oil acts as the internal phase while water serves as the external medium, making it an oil-based emulsion suitable for non-greasy and easily washable applications.

In contrast, Water-in-Oil (W/O) creams consist of water droplets dispersed within a continuous oil phase. Here, water forms the internal phase and oil acts as the external medium, resulting in a water-based emulsion. These formulations tend to be more occlusive and are ideal for dry or dehydrated skin due to their ability to retain moisture^[5,6,7].

METHODOLOGY

6.1 PLANT PROFILE

EUPHORBIA MILII –

Euphorbia milii, the **crown-of-thorns**, **Christ plant** or **Christ's thorn**, is a species of flowering plant in the spurge family, Euphorbiaceae, native to Madagascar. The species commemorates Baron Milius, once Governor of Réunion, who introduced the species to France in 1821^[9,10].

Fig.no 3: *Euphorbia milii* plant

- **Botanical Name :** *Euphorbia milii* Des Moul.
- **Synonyms:** *Euphorbia splendens* subsp. *Bojeri* (Hook.) Denis
- **Common Name :** Crown of Thorns,

- **English:** Christ-plant, Christ-thorn
- **Spanish:** corona de Cristo, espina santa, martirio
- **French :** épine du Christ
- **Chinese:** tie hai tang
- **Scientific name:** *Euphorbia milii*
- **Family:** Euphorbiaceae
- **Plant Form :** Shrub
- **Genus:** Euphorbia
- **Kingdom:** Plantae
- **Order:** Malpighiales

About *Euphorbia milii* Plant:

- **Habit:** A small, armed shrub with stem fleshy, with long spines and bluish-white colour and milky latex.
- **Leaves:** Alternate, oblong, acute or obovate, mucronate, spines on the branches in pairs, in between each pair of spines, is a reduced branch which bears pairs of small spines. In between each pair of spines a leaf is developed, therefore, the spines are modified stipules.
- **Inflorescence:** Cyathium
- **Flowers:**
 - Cyathia grouped dichotomously, stalked from the axils of upper leaves.
 - The peduncle is divided into two successively three times and the cyathia are seated on the ultimate pedicles.
 - Each cyathium is supported by two, petaloid, crimson or scarlet, orbicular mucronate bracts which have fused to the involucre in their lower part.
 - The involucre bears at the top margin, 5 broad, rounded glands, alternate, with the glands is a reddish scale or bracteole. Inside the involucre, there are many male flowers,

consisting of a stalked stamen with two-anther lobes.

- Ovary 3-locur, 3-lobed, with one ovule in each cell, styles 3, connate for half their length, each divided into a pair, short stigmas.
- **Flowering and Fruiting Time:** Throughout the year.
- **Significance:** It is very popular in all gardens.

Leaves:

Euphorbia milii, commonly known as Crown of Thorns, has fleshy, bright green, obovate leaves that are typically found on new stem growth, and are known to drop off as the stems mature, leaving a spiny appearance [8,9,10].

Morphology Features:

The "songosongo" plant, also known as Euphorbia Milii or crown of thorns, is indigenous to Madagascar. It is a woody succulent prickly shrub that reaches a height of 1.5 to 2 meters (5-7 feet). The spines become straight and narrow when they reach a length of 3 cm. The oblong, acute-shaped, fleshy green leaves can reach lengths of 3-3.5 cm and widths of 1.5 cm. These tiny, cup-shaped flowers, which range in hue from red to pink to white, are hung in two petal-like bracts and measure up to 12 mm. Since euphorbia thrives in warmer temperatures, it produces flowers throughout the year but especially in the spring and summer [10,11,12].

Chemical Constituents:

Euphorbia milii contains a variety of phytochemicals, including terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, and tannins. These compounds are believed to contribute to the plant's various medicinal properties. Specific examples of phytochemicals

found in *E. milii* include beta-amyrin acetate, beta-sitosterol, cycloartenol, lupeol, euphol, and flavonoids. The medicinal values of the plants depend on the presence of certain chemical substances (secondary metabolites) that are involved in production of different kinds of effects on human body [13,14,15].

Pharmacological Activity:

Fig.no 4: Pharmacological activity

6.2 DETERMINATION OF TOTAL ASH:

PROCEDURE

1. About 2 g of the powdered drug was weighed accurately in a tared silica crucible.
2. Crucible with powdered drug was incinerated in muffle furnace by gradually increasing heat (temperature) at 500-800°C until freed from carbon.
3. After complete incineration, furnace was off and crucible was remained in it till temperature fall down.
4. The crucible was removed from the furnace and cooled after the incineration about 1 hour in a desiccator.
5. The ash was weighed and percentage of total ash with reference to the air dried sample was calculated.

The total ash value for given sample *Euphorbia milli* was found to be 12 % W/W.

Formula:

Total ash = (Weight of ash/Weight of sample) x100

Fig.no 5: Determination of total ash

6.3 DETERMINATION OF ACID-INSOLUBLE ASH VALUE:

Procedure:

1. Using 25 ml of dilute HCl, wash the ash from the dish used for total ash into a 100 ml beaker.
2. Place a mere guaze over a Bunsen burner and boil for five minutes.
3. Filter through an 'ashless' filter paper, wash the residue twice with hot water.
4. Ignite a crucible in the flame, cool and weigh.
5. Put the filter paper and residue together into the crucible heat gently until vapours cease to be evolved and then more strongly until all carbon has been removed.
6. Cool in a desiccator.
7. Weigh the residue and calculate acid-insoluble ash of the crude drug with refer to the air-dried sample of the crude drug.

Formula:

Acid -insoluble ash value = (Weight of acid - insoluble ash/Weight of sample) x 100

Fig no.6: Acid insoluble ash value

6.4 DETERMINATION OF WATER-SOLUBLE ASH:

Procedure:

1. Using 25 ml of water, wash the ash from the dish used for total ash into a 100 ml beaker.
2. Place a mere guaze over a Bunsen burner and boil for five minutes.
3. Filter through an 'ashless' filter paper, wash the residue twice with hot water.
4. Ignite a crucible in the flame, cool and weigh.
5. Put the filter paper and residue together into the crucible heat gently until vapours cease to be evolved and then more strongly until all carbon has been removed.
6. Cool in a desiccator.
7. Weigh the residue and calculate water-insoluble ash of the crude drug with refer to the air-dried sample of the crude drug.

Formula:

Water-insoluble ash value = (Weight of water-insoluble ash/Weight of sample) x100

Fig.no:7: Water -insoluble ash

6.5 DETERMINATION OF LOSS ON DRYING (LOD) Maceration:

Procedure:

1. Weigh accurately 2g of the powdered drug into a weighed flat and thin porcelain dish.
2. Dry in the oven at 100°C or 105°C, until two consecutive weight do not differ by more than 0.5 mg.
3. Cool in a desiccator and weigh. The loss in weight is usually recorded as moisture.

Formula:

Loss on Drying = $(\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight after drying} / \text{Initial weight}) \times 100$ ^[16,17,18,19].

Fig no.8: Loss on Drying

6.6 METHOD OF EXTRACTION:

► Infusion:

- It consist of pouring water over the drugs and
- Then allowing it to keep in contact with water for the stated period, usually 30 minutes, with occasional stirring and Processes used for extraction
- finally filtering off the liquid.

Fig.no. 9: Infusion

In this extraction method, coarsely powdered plant material—such as leaves, stem bark, or root bark—is placed in a container. A suitable solvent (menstruum) is then added until the material is fully submerged. The container is sealed and allowed to stand for a minimum of three days. During this period, the mixture is stirred or, if kept in a bottle, shaken occasionally to facilitate thorough extraction. After the extraction period, the liquid portion (micelle) is separated from the solid residue (marc) using filtration or decantation. The micelle is then subjected to evaporation, either in an oven or over a water bath, to remove the solvent. This method is especially appropriate for extracting compounds from thermolabile (heat-sensitive) plant materials.

Fig.no10: Maceration

Decoction:

This method involves continuous hot extraction using a measured amount of water as the solvent. The plant material, which is first dried, ground, and finely powdered, is placed in a clean container. Water is added and the mixture is stirred thoroughly. Heat is applied throughout the procedure to accelerate the extraction of active constituents. The entire process typically takes around 15 minutes. This technique is ideal for

extracting compounds that are both water-soluble and stable under heat.

Fig no.11: Decoction

Percolation:

This extraction method uses an apparatus known as a percolator, which is a narrow, cone-shaped glass vessel with openings at both ends. The plant material, which is dried, ground, and finely powdered, is first moistened with a suitable solvent in a clean container. After moistening, an additional amount of solvent is added, and the mixture is allowed to stand for about 4 hours. Following this, the material is transferred into the percolator with the lower opening closed and left undisturbed for 24 hours to allow saturation. Then, more solvent is poured from the top until the plant material is fully saturated. The bottom outlet is then opened, and the extract is allowed to drip slowly. During the process, more solvent is added gradually, enabling gravity to carry it through the plant material, facilitating extraction. The solvent addition is stopped once approximately 75% of the total intended volume has been used. The extract is collected, and any remaining liquid is separated through filtration and decantation. The residual plant material (marc) is pressed to recover remaining extract, and finally, enough solvent is added to make up the required volume of the preparation. [20,21].

Fig no.12: Percolator

SOXHLET EXTRACTION:

Soxhlet extractor was invented in 1879 by Franz von Soxhlet, a German chemist. The original use of this apparatus was the extraction of a lipid from a solid material. It is an apparatus used in the laboratory for extracting a compound with a limited solubility in a solvent and where the impurity is insoluble in that solvent. This is one of the conventional solid/liquid extraction method which consists in extracting directly from the raw material using a solvent and an extractor.

Chemical:

The chemical solvents and other products that have been used in the experiments and methods are the following:

- Distilled water
- Whatman filter
- Ethanol (C_2H_6O) was supplied by Molar Chemicals Kft, purity: 99.5%.
- Diethyl Ether (C_2H_5) was supplied by molar chemical Kft, purity: 98%%.

Method of extraction:

For this operation, an approximate amount of 50 g was measured into the paper thimble placed inside the chamber. Also 240 ml of solvent was

introduced in the solvent flask. three solvents with different polarities were applied: ether, chloroform and 70% ethanol. The Soxhlet apparatus was connected to a cooler and the round bottom flask containing the solvent was immersed in silicon oil. First the cooling water of condenser was turned on, then the heating element of silicon bath was switched on for the solvent is heated, and the extraction can start. The extraction run until the solvent in the Soxhlet apparatus became transparent again, which showed the end of extraction. It took around 3 days (18 hours more or less) in the case of raw material with diethyl ether, and one day extract with chloroform and 4 days (24 hours) for raw material with 96% ethanol extraction. After the Soxhlet extraction was done, the evaporation of the liquid is necessary in order to get the extract without solvent. For this, each flask had to be evaporated in the rotary evaporator using a vacuum pump and a control valve. After this step only the extract obtained as a product remains in the flask, which is collected in a sample bottle. The extracted material was dried and discarded. The solvent evaporated and condensed is collected in another flask and returned to a bottle for reuse^[22].

Fig no.13: Soxhlet Extraction

Estimation of total tannin content:

In this method, 100 mg of extract was accurately weighed and was dissolved in 100 ml of methanol to make the stock solution. This was further diluted 5 times and 1 ml of this resultant solution was transferred to a test tube. To this 7 ml. of methanol was added followed by addition of 0.5 mL. of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 1.5 mL. of 20% Na₂CO₃ solution. The final volume was made up to 10 mL with methanol. Tannic acid was used as a reference standard for this estimation. The final solution was shaken vigorously to achieve a proper distribution and was kept for 15 min in dark. Further, absorbance was recorded at 775 nm against blank using UV spectrometer and the total tannin contents was expressed in terms of mg/g tannic acid equivalent^[23].

Graph Calculation

Fig no.14: Total tannic content

6.11 Thin Layer Chromatography:

Steps to Prepare TLC Plate:

1. Prepare the slurry:

- Mix 1 part silica gel G with 2–3 parts distilled water in a beaker.
- Stir quickly to get a uniform slurry.

2. Coat the glass plate:

- Pour the slurry onto one end of the glass plate.
- Spread it evenly using a spreader or TLC applicator.
- Aim for a uniform thickness of ~0.25 mm.

3. Air dry:

Let the coated plate stand vertically for about 10–15 minutes to remove surface moisture.

4. Activate the plate:

Place the plate in an oven at 110–120°C for 30 minutes to remove all moisture and activate the adsorbent.

5. Cool and store:

Allow the plates to cool

6. Sample Preparation:

Dissolve tannic acid in a suitable solvent like methanol or ethanol to make a dilute solution (~1–2 mg/mL).

7. Spotting the Plate:

- Using a capillary tube, apply a small spot of the tannic acid solution about 1 cm from the bottom edge of the TLC plate.
- Allow the spot to dry completely. You may repeat the spotting 2–3 times to concentrate it.

8. Prepare the Mobile Phase:

- Mix solvents: n-Butanol: Acetic acid: Water (4:1:5).
- Pour into a TLC chamber (jar or beaker with lid).
- Place a piece of filter paper in the chamber to saturate the atmosphere (improves separation).

9. Develop the Plate:

- Place the TLC plate vertically in the chamber. The solvent level must be below the sample spot.
- Close the chamber and allow the solvent to rise until it's about 3/4th of the plate height.
- Remove the plate and mark the solvent front with a pencil immediately.

10. Dry the Plate:

Air-dry or gently warm to remove solvent vapors.

11. Visualization:

- Spray with FeCl₃ solution (1% ferric chloride in ethanol or water).
- Heat gently if required. Tannic acid spots appear blue-black or greenish.

12. Calculation of Rf value:

$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance travelled by the solute}}{\text{Distance travelled by the solvent front}}$ ^[24,25].

Fig no.15: TLC plate

6.12 PREPARATION OF CREAM

PROCEDURE:

1. All ingredients were weighed accurately.

2. Accurately weigh beeswax and liquid paraffin and heat them together in a beaker at 70–75°C until completely melted. This mixture forms the oil phase (cream base).
3. In a separate beaker, dissolve borax, methyl paraben, and aluminium sulphate in distilled water and heat to the same temperature as the oil phase (around 70–75°C). This is the aqueous phase and acts as the preservative vehicle.
4. Gradually add the hot aqueous phase to the oil phase with continuous stirring to form a uniform cream base. Continue stirring until a homogenous emulsion forms.
5. Allow the emulsion to cool down to below 40°C while stirring slowly.
6. Add mentha, Euphorbia milli extract, and prednisolone while stirring gently to ensure even distribution.
7. Add starch to act as a thickener and stabilizer.
8. Incorporate tartrazine (colouring agent) and vanilla (flavouring agent) in quantities sufficient for desired appearance and fragrance.
9. Mix thoroughly until the cream is smooth and homogenous.
10. Transfer the prepared cream into clean, dry containers.
11. Label properly and store in a cool, dry place^[27,28].

Fig.no. 16: Formulated Cream

FORMULATION COMPONENT:**Table no. 1: Formulation of cream**

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity Formulation F1 (20g)	Quantity Formulation F2 (20g)	Quantity Formulation F3 (20g)	Roles of ingredients
1.	Beeswax	5g	5g	5.5g	Cream base
2.	Liquid Paraffin	7g	7.5g	7g	Cream base
3.	Borax	0.2g	0.2g	0.2g	Emulsifier
4.	Water	4.5g	4g	4g	vehicle
5.	Methyl paraben	0.2g	0.2g	0.2g	Preservative
6.	Aluminium Sulphate	1g	1g	1g	Astringent
7.	Starch	0.2g	0.2g	0.2g	Thickeners
8.	Mentha	0.5g	0.5g	0.5g	Colling and smoothing effects
9.	Euphorbia milli extract	1g	1g	1g	Antioxidant, Anti-microbial
10.	Prednisolone	0.4g	0.4g	0.4g	Anti-inflammatory
11.	Tartarazine	q.s	q.s	q.s	Colouring agent
12.	Vanilla	q.s	q.s	q.s	Flavouring agent

6.13 Evaluation of cream –**1) Evaluation of cream pH of the cream:**

Using normal buffer solutions, the pH meter was performed calibration. Approximately 0.5 g of the cream was balanced and dissolved in 50.0 ml of distilled water, calculating its pH. In a 100ml beaker, 5 ± 0.01 g of the cream was correctly measured. 45ml of water was applied and the cream was spread therein. Using the pH meter, the pH of the suspension was estimated at 27°C. The cream pH was found to be in the range of 4.5 to 6.5 which is good for the PH of the skin. All the formulations showed pH closer to the appropriate skin.

2) Organoleptic evaluation:

The cream thus acquired was evaluated for its organoleptic properties, such as color, odor, and condition. The appearance of the cream was measured and graded by its roughness and Colour.

3) Homogeneity:

The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch.

4) Spreadability studies:

Spreadability is expressed in terms of your time in seconds taken by two slides to slide far- away from the formulation, placed between, under the appliance of a particular load. Two glass slides of ordinary dimensions were selected. The formulation whose spreadability had to be determined was placed over one of the slides and the other slide was placed on top of the formulations was crammed between the two slides across the length of 5 cm alongside the slide. 100 g weight was placed upon the upper slide so as that the formulation between the two slides was pressed uniformly to form a thin layer. The load was removed and thus the quite formulation adhering to the slides was scrapped off and one of the slides was fixed on which the formulation was placed. The second movable slide was placed over

it, with one end tied to a string to which load could be applied with the help of a simple pulley and a pan. A 30g weight was placed on the pan and thus the time taken for the upper slide to travel the space of 5.0cm and separate distant from the lower slide under the direction of the load was noted.

The Spreadability (S) are often determined using the formula.

$$\text{Spreadability} = m \times l / t$$

m = weight tied to the upper slide (25g)

l=length of glass slide (5cm)

T = time taken in seconds. [29,30]

6) Antimicrobial test:

Protocol- The Nutrient agar media was used. *Staphylococcus aureus* microorganism culture was used. Incubation time was setup for 24hrs.

Method-Agar bore well diffusion method.

Procedure- *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram +ve bacteria) suspension was introduced in each plates & 40ml of sterile nutrient agar media was poured into each sterilized plates. The plates were left on the flat solid surface & allow to harden. In each plate 1cup, 10mm in diameter was bored in the

medium with cork borer. The disks of agar were removed by sterilized dissecting needle while being careful not to damage the cups. In each plate equal amount of cream formulation having same strength was placed in the cup & the plates were incubated at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24hrs.in incubator. The entire operation was carried out under aseptic condition & zone of inhibition was calculated. The zone of inhibition obtained for prepared formulation was showed in figure no.17^[31,32].

Fig.no.17: Antimicrobial test

QUALITATIVE TESTS FOR PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING^[16,17,18]

1. Detection of alkaloids

Table no. 2: Detection of Alkaloids

Sr.no	Tests	Procedure	Observations
1)	Dragendorff's/ Kraut's test	Few mL filtrate a + 1- 2 mL Dragendorff's reagent	A reddish- brown precipitate
2)	Mayer test	Few ml extract +1ml mayer reagent	A cream colour precipitate
3)	Wagner's test	Few mL filtrate + 1-2 drops of Wagner's reagent (Along the sides of test tube)	A brown/reddish precipitate
4)	Hager test	Few mL filtrate a + 1- 2 mL Hager's reagents	A creamy white/yellow precipitate

Fig no. 18 : Alkaloids

2. Detection of reducing sugar

Table no. 3: Detection of Reducing sugar

Sr.no	Tests	Procedure	Observations
1)	Benedict's test	0.5mL filtrate + 0.5mL Benedict's reagent + Boiled for 2 min.	Green/ yellow/ red colour
2)	Fehling's test	1mL each of Fehling's solution A & B + 1mL filtrate + boiled in water bath	A red precipitate

Fig. no 19: Reducing sugar

3. Detection of Cardiac Glycoside

Table no. 4: Detection of Cardiac Glycoside

Sr.no	Tests	Procedure	Observations
1)	Keller Killiani test	1ml filtrate + 3ml glacial acetic acid + 2 drops ferric chloride sol + 3ml conc. H ₂ SO ₄ added to the sides of test tube.	A reddish brown ring layer
2)	Bromine water test	Plant extract + few mL of bromine water A yellow precipitate	A yellow precipitate

Fig. no 20: Cardiac glycoside

4. Detection of flavonoids

Table no. 5: Detection of Flavonoids

Sr.no	Tests	Procedure	Observations
1)	Lead acetate test	1mL plant extract + few drops of 10% lead acetate solution	A yellow precipitate
2)	Ferric chloride test	Extract aqueous solution + few drops 10% ferric chloride solution	A green precipitate
3)	Ammonia test	Filtrate + 5mL dil. Ammonia solution + conc. H ₂ SO ₄	A yellow colour

4)	Alkali test	Test solution +10% aq. NaOH Solution	A yellow orange colour	Fig. no 21: Flavonoids
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5. Detection of phenolic compound

Table no. 6: Detection of Phenolic Compound

Sr.no	Tests	Procedure	Observations
1)	Iodine test	1mL extract + few drops of dil. Iodine sol.	A transient red colour
2)	Potassium dichromate	Plant extract + few drops of potassium dichromate solution	A dark colour
3)	Lead acetate test	Plant extract is dissolved in 5mL distilled water + 3mL of 10% lead acetate sol.	A white precipitate

Fig. no 22: Phenolic Compound

6. Detection of Tannins

Table no. 7: Detection of Tannins

Sr.no	Test	Procedure	Observation
1)	Ferric chloride Solution	Plant Extract + few drops of ferric chloride solution.	A bluish green or bluish black
2)	Gold Beater Test	Extract + Gold beater reagent	A brown or black colour

Fig. no 23: Tannins

RESULT AND DISCUSSION-

A] PREFORMULATION PARAMETERS

1) Morphology Characteristics of *Euphorbia milii*

Table no.8: Morphology Characteristics of *Euphorbia milii*

Sr.no	Properties	Characteristic
1.	Shape	oblong, acute or obovate of leaves, tiny, cup-shaped flowers
2.	Size	lengths of 3-3.5 cm and widths of 1.5 cm leaves,

		hung in two petal-like bracts and measure up to 12 mm flowers.
3.	Colour	freshly green leaves, red to pink to white flowers
4.	Odour	Not fragrant

2) Physicochemical parameters of *Euphorbia milii*

Table no.9: Physicochemical parameters of *Euphorbia milii*

Sr.no	Parameters	Result
1.	Percentage Ash value	12% w/w
2.	Extractive value (ethanolic extract)	5%
3.	Extractive value (water extract)	11%
4.	Loss of drying (moisture content)	25%

3) To develop various extraction methods of *Euphorbia milii* crude drug in 100 ml of solvent

Table no.10: Extraction methods of *Euphorbia milii* crude drug in 100 ml of solvent

Sr. No.	Methods	Solvents	% Total quantity
1.	Infusion	100 ml distilled water	90 ml
2.	Maceration	70 ml ethanol +30 ml water	2 g (25 ml)
3.	Decoction	100 ml distilled water	1 g (90 ml)
4.	Percolation	25 ml ethanol	1 g (15 ml)
5.	Soxhlet extraction	70 ml ethanol +30 water	22 g (250 ml)

4) Phytochemical Screening parameters of *Euphorbia milli*.

Table no.11: Phytochemical Screening *Euphorbia milli*

Sr.no	Plant constituents	Test reagent	Aqueous extract	Ethanolic extract
1.	Alkaloids	Dragendorff's reagent Mayer's reagent Hager's reagent Wagner's reagent	+ + + +	- - - +
2.	Reducing sugar	Benedict's test Fehling's test	+ +	- -
3.	Cardiac glycoside	Keller Killiani test Bromine water test	+ +	- -
4.	flavonoids	Lead acetate test Ferric chloride test Ammonia test Alkali test	+ + - +	+ + + -
5.	phenolic compound	Iodine test Potassium dichromate Lead acetate test	- + +	+ - +
6.	tannins	Ferric chloride Solution	+	+

(+) sign indicate presence (-) sign indicate absence

5) Quantitative estimation of total tannin content

Table no.12: Estimation of total tannin content

Sr. No.	Solvent	Total tannin content quantity
1.	Ethanol	0.97mg/ml
2.	Water	0.79mg/ml

6) Thin Layer Chromatography:

Table no.13: Thin Layer Chromatography

Sr. No.	Stationary phase	Mobile phase	Rf
1.	Silica gel G	n-Butanol: Acetic acid: Water (4:1:5).	0.52

B) FORMULATION STUDY-

1) Organoleptic evaluation:

Organoleptic evaluation revealed that all formulations of herbal multipurpose cream have semisolid in nature, yellow and smooth in appearance and texture.

Table no.14: Organoleptic Properties of cream

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameter	Inhouse F1(20g)	Inhouse F2(20g)	Inhouse F3(20g)
1.	State	semisolid	semisolid	semisolid
2.	Colour	green	green	green
3.	Odour	aromatic	aromatic	aromatic
4.	Texture	smooth	smooth	smooth
5.	Type of emulsion	o/w	o/w	o/w

2) Pharmaceutical parameters:

Evaluation related to pH are summarized in Table no.15. All the 3 batches exhibit values in acceptable criteria.

Table no.15: Formulated & Evaluation of cream

Sr. No.	Evaluation parameters	Acceptance criteria	Inhouse F1 (20g)	Inhouse F2 (20g)	Inhouse F3 (20g)
1.	pH	4.5 to 6.5	5.5	6	6
2.	spreadability	12.5 g cm/sec	11 g cm/sec	12 g cm/sec	12 g cm/sec

3.	Viscosity	Less viscous	Less viscous	Less viscous	Less viscous
4.	Homogeneity	Good	Good	Good	Good
5.	Apperance	Not change in colour			

Table no.16: Spreadability test

Formulation	Time (sec)	Spreadability (g cm/sec)
Inhouse F1	45 sec	11 g cm/sec
Inhouse F2	50 sec	12 g cm/sec
Inhouse F3	55 sec	12 g cm/sec

The prepared herbal face pack was evaluated for stability studies and the results are show In Table no.16 No change in colour, odour, texture, smoothness and pH was observed on room temperature and on 40°.

3) Stability:

Table no.17: Stability of cream

Sr. No.	Parameters	Room temperature (above 40 °C)	Inhouse F1 (20g)	Inhouse F2 (20g)	Inhouse F3 (20g)
1	Colour	No change	No change	No change	No change
2	Odour	No change	No change	No change	No change
3	Texture	Fine	Fine	Fine	Fine
4	Smoothness	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
5	pH	6	6	5.5	5.5

Stability tests performed at different temperatures over a period of one month revealed the inert nature of the cream in the terms of color, odor, appearance, texture and pH.

4) Antimicrobial test:

The antimicrobial study of formulation revealed that herbal cream possess good zone of inhibition. Batch F1 had high value of zone of inhibition than batch F2&F3.

Table no. 18: Antimicrobial testing

Sr. No.	Parameters	Zone of inhibition (mm)
1.	Inhouse F1	13mm
2.	Inhouse F2	9mm
3.	Marketed F3	15mm
4.	Standard (Amoxyclav 625mg)	17mm

DISCUSSION-

The formulation of an anti-haemorrhoid cream incorporating both prednisolone and Euphorbia milii extract offers a synergistic approach to effectively manage the symptoms of hemorrhoids, such as inflammation, pain, and vascular congestion effectively. This dual-approach formulation aims to harness the strengths of both agents — fast symptom control and long-term mucosal recovery — for enhanced therapeutic

efficacy in hemorrhoid treatment. According to the obtained results the confirmation of *Euphorbia milli* leaf extract is carried out by (method of Maceration) performing Thin layer Chromatography Method. The ethanolic extract of *Euphorbia milli* leaves did not cause damage to the skin. This is due to the active compound of the ethanol extract of *Euphorbia milli* leaves which is an anti-inflammatory. The Ash value of *Euphorbia milli* was found to be 12%w/w. The Loss of Drying was occur 25% Extractive value found to be 5%. The *Euphorbia milli* leaf ethanol extract contains flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and steroids. The active compounds that act as anti-inflammatory are Tannins. The formulation aims to leverage the fast-acting effect of prednisolone and the safety and supportive healing potential of *Euphorbia milii*. Evaluation parameters like pH, viscosity, spreadability, drug content, and in vitro release should be optimized to ensure compatibility and stability between the two actives.

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